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SELF DIRECTED LEARNING – OPPORTUNITIES TO EDUCATION

Dr Mrs Sharmila L. Mascarenhas

Assistant Professor, St. Ann’s College of Education (Autonomous), Mangaluru- 575001

Email: mayfair23@yahoo.in

ABSTRACT

In the fast advancing world today, one cannot be complacent and need to be prepared to adjust to the demanding need of the day. As the world progresses towards technological advancements, information has become more accessible for learners to form their knowledge. To face these challenges and cope up with the competition, every human being has to be well equipped with skills to undertake every situation which is possible only through self regulation and self motivation. The role of the teacher has evolved from being the disseminator of knowledge to being facilitator in the process of constructing knowledge. This process is guided through Self-Directed Learning, a key feature in the learning process. To be able to learn in a Self-directed manner, it is important to develop an awareness of one's ability to Self-learn and then to implement appropriate and effective strategies to Self-learning. This paper focuses on the historical picture, theories and opportunities of Self Directed Learning to the learning process in particular and Education in general.

Theme: Innovation in Education

Keywords: Self Directed Learning, Personal Responsibility Orientation Model, Historical picture of Self directed Learning

1.0 Objective: To analyze Self Directed Learning as a Pedagogical Approach to Education.

2.0 Introduction

The present education system is a closed system where the whole control of the learning process is with the teacher or with an equivalent authority which frames the curriculum. It is greatly teacher directed as the curriculum pre-decides what is to be learned, why it is to be learned, how it is to be learned, when, where and at what age it has to be learned. As a result the learners become a passive recipient of knowledge with little or no control over his learning. The National Curriculum Framework 2005 lays a strong emphasis on the need to recognize the child as a

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natural learner, and knowledge as the outcome of the child’s own activity. It has stated

“In their everyday lives outside the school we witness the children enjoying the curiosity, inventiveness and constant querying. They actively engage with the world around them, exploring, responding, inventing and working things out, and making meaning.” – National Curriculum Framework 2005

The NEP 2020 emphasizes the learning process to be more holistic, integrated, enjoyable and engaging. The focus should be on critical thinking by dipping the curriculum content which gives way to introduce and initiate experiential learning in the teaching learning process.

This poses a great challenge for the teacher to meet the individual needs of learners in a classroom setup characterized by multiple abilities, achievement and social development, hence, leading to increased demands on teacher’s time and effort. Yet, in spite the best efforts a classroom may not be able to completely meet the needs of the pupil. This states that a satisfactory learning experience could be achieved only by building self directedness among the pupils where the pupil takes complete responsibility for his learning process which comes to be known as Self Directed Learning.

People need to adapt themselves to the demanding requirements of the society. Socializing just does not mean mingling with others but behaving in a way that is acceptable to all and this comes only from Self-directed behaviors. These skills of directing oneself into are not new to mankind. It is an observed fact that many adults indulge in Self Directed Learning to gain new skills, knowledge and attitudes to improve their work performance and others to improve their family life and health, enjoy the arts and physical recreation, participate in a lobby or simply increase their intellectual capital.

Guglielmino (2008) has explicated Self Directed Learning in terms of context, activation, and universality. She argues that Self Directed Learning is an innate, basic and natural characteristic of human beings when encountering challenges and this characteristic varies on the continuum, depending on situations.

The habits of organized study cannot be implanted in human beings all of a sudden. It is a process through which man can habituate himself to these skills. The only means of transforming the individual from the past to the presently required skills is Education. The trend of education today is slowly changing from mere absorption of information, as that of the past, to a selective choice of useful skills. Hence education needs to focus more on developing essential skills where an

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individual becomes wholly responsible for what he does and also the education needs to make use of these skills in its course.

Schools, traditionally associated with preparing young learners to take their places in an adult social and economic world, are put under increasing pressures to implement pedagogical changes that will support students and provide them with a positive start to a lifetime of learning. Making learning part of life is an essential challenge for inventing the future of our societies. Lifelong learning is a necessity rather than a possibility or a luxury to be considered. Therefore education has to find ways to help an individual to learn what he wants to learn by himself with self based efforts. Self Directed Learning is a convenient means towards this achievement.

3.0 Background of the Study

3.1 Historical picture of Self Directed Learning

Self Directed Learning is the latest trend that has been catching up in every field of study, may it be professional or educational organizations. The beginning of this idea could be dated back to the times when man started living a settled life. He started discovering and learning on his own, the methods of lighting fire, growing his own food and other necessities of life.

In the later years as we notice self study played a significant role in the lives of Greek philosophers such as Socrates, Plato and Aristotle due to the lack of formal education system. Though this concept existed from classical antiquity yet Self Directed Learning came into awareness as a systematic concept only in the recent past.

Early scholarly efforts to understand Self Directed Learning took place some 150 years ago in United States.

- **Craik (1840)** documented the self education efforts of several people.
- **Smiles (1859)** of Great Britain published a book entitled ‘Self Help’, the book much-admired the significance of personal development.
- Ground work was laid through the interpretation of **Houle (1961)** of University of Chicago, Illinois where he categorized people based on the reasons for participation in learning, and one of his category was identified as Self Directed learners in the succeeding research.
- **Knowles (1975)** popularized in North America the term andragogy with corresponding adult instructional processes. His 1975 publication ‘Self Directed Learning’ provided foundational definitions and assumptions that guided much subsequent researches.

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- **Guglielmino (1977)** developed the Self Directed Learning Readiness Scale (SDLRS), an instrument subsequently used by many researchers to measure Self Directed Learning aspects with numerous characteristics.
- **Tough (1979)** a Canadian researcher made efforts to analyze self-directed teaching activities and subsequent research with additional subject resulted in a book titled ‘**The Adult learning Projects (1979)**’.
- Establishment of an International Symposium on Self Directed Learning in **1986** by **Dr Huey Long** and his colleagues
- The latest International Self Directed Learning Symposium was held in February 2020 in Florida which was a platform to discuss the developments and applications of Self Directed Learning.

3.2 Review of Related Literature

Presently research related to Self Directed Learning has been in full progress and could be classified under several classifications. Although initially Self Directed Learning emerged as a part of Adult Education today it has expanded to different fields of study. The focus of these studies varies from clarifying the concept of Self Directed Learning to studying the approaches which can be useful in fostering Self Directed Learning.

A review of related literature was done to strengthen the rationale of the study to be conducted. While reviewing the related literature, the researcher found certain studies which revealed the importance of Self-directed Learning in the field of education. **Houle (1961)** conducted a qualitative research study among 22 adult learners and revealed that adult learners were classified into three categories namely, goal-oriented learners, activity-oriented learners, learning-oriented learners. **Herlo (2017)** conducted a quantitative study on Self-directed Learning on teacher training studies programs and reported that self-directed learning has the potential to lead, on both cognitive and emotional-motivational level, to improved learning outcomes as opposed to traditional methods. **Nasri (2017)** conducted a qualitative study on Self-directed Learning through the eyes of the teacher educator which suggested that the educators must build a collaborative relationship with the learner, recognize learning resources and restrictions in the process of implementation of Self-directed Learning. **Minh Tri, Van Hong and Vo (2017)** conducted an empirical study on Self-directed Learning in the context of internationalization in TVET in

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Vietnam and concluded that Self-consciousness was a necessity among learners and Self-directed Learning is ideal in this fluctuating globalized society for anyone who desires for lifelong learning. An empirical study was conducted by **Maung, Zorani and Abdullah (2017)** titled ‘Factors influencing Development of Self-directed Learning in a Higher Education Environment’, the result revealed that it is advisable to integrate Self-directed Learning strategies in Secondary School Level. **Devi, Bhat, Ramya, Ravichandran, Kanungo (2017)** conducted a experimental study titled, Self-directed learning to enhance active learning among the Second-year undergraduate medical students in Microbiology and concluded that a significant increase was shown between the Pre-test and Post-test scores of the Medical students and students understanding, simulated reasoning, active participation and collaboration.

Studies revealed that Self-directed Learning has a greater influence on Education and proved that the learners when directed towards Self-learning tend to thrive in the real comprehension of the relevant concepts and hence better academic distinction is achieved. It also enables the self-confidence of learners through emotional motivation.

3.3 Conceptual and Theoretical Framework of Self Directed Learning

Self Directed Learning is a concept related to both the learning process and the learner. It is characterized by the external characteristics of an instructional process and internal characteristics of the learner.

3.3.1 Concept of Self Directed Learning

Self-directed learning describes a process in which individuals take the initiative with or without the help of others, in diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying resources for learning, choosing and implementing learning strategies and evaluating learning outcomes (**Knowles 1975**)

Knowles puts forward three immediate reasons for Self Directed Learning.

- There is convincing evidence that people who take initiative in learning learn more things and learn better. They learn with a purpose and with greater motivation.
- Self-directed learning is more in tune with our natural processes of psychological development.
- The new developments in education placed an intense responsibility on the learners to take

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initiative of their own learning.

Self Directed Learning refers to a process whereby the learner assumes a major responsibility for the initiation, planning, implementation and monitoring of their own learning (**Boekaerts, Pintrich and Zeidner, 2000**)

Self-direction in learning refers to both the external characteristics of an instructional process and the internal characteristics of the learner, where the individual assumes primary responsibility for a learning experience (**Brockett and Hiemstra 1991**)

Self Directed Learning is any increase in knowledge, skill, accomplishment, or personal development that an individual selects and brings about by his or her own efforts using any method in any circumstances at any time (**Gibbons (2002)**)

Self Directed Learning can be viewed as a "set of generic, finite behaviors; as a belief system reflecting and evolving from a process of self-initiated learning activity; or as an ideal state of the mature self-actualized learner (**Kasworm 1983**)

3.3.2 Models of Self Directed learning

Framework for Understanding Self Direction - Personal Responsibility Orientation Model (Brockett & Hiemstra, 1991)

From: Brockett, R.G. & Hiemstra, R. (1991). *Self-Direction in Adult Learning: Perspectives on Theory, Research, and Practice*. London and New York: Routledge.

Figure 1: Personal Responsibility Orientation Model

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Brockett and Hiemstra (1991) synthesized various ideas about Self Directed Learning and conceptualized the **Personal Responsibility Orientation (PRO) model**. This model identifies the differences and similarities between Self Directed Learning as an instructional method and learner self-direction, based on personality characteristics. As can be seen in Figure1, the point of departure for understanding self- direction is personal responsibility and empowerment. Personal responsibility refers to individuals assuming possession for their own thoughts and actions.

On the left side of the model, Self Directed Learning refers to the actual teaching and learning transactions or what we refer to as those factors external to the learner. Learner self-direction refers to the personal orientation of individuals engaged in a learning process. This involves a learner’s personality characteristics, or those factors internal to the individual such as self-concept.

In terms of learning, it is an ability or willingness of individuals to take control that determines any potential for self-direction. This means that learners have choices about the directions they pursue.

Brockett and Hiemstra view the term Self Directed Learning as an instructional process centering on such activities as assessing needs, securing learning resources, implementing learning activities and evaluating learning. Hiemstra & Sisco, (1990) refer to this as individualizing instruction, a process focusing on characteristics of the teaching-learning transaction.

The PRO model’s final component is represented by the circle in Figure 1 that encompasses all other elements. While the individual's personality characteristics and the teaching and learning process are starting points for understanding self-direction, the social context provides an arena in which the learning activity or results are created. Brockett and Hiemstra recommend that self-direction in learning be used as an umbrella definition recognizing those external factors facilitating learners taking primary responsibility for learning and those internal factors or personality characteristics that incline one toward personal empowerment or accepting such responsibility.

Garrison’s Model of Self Directed Learning

Garrison (1997) suggests learners assume personal responsibility (motivation), collaborative control of the cognitive (self-monitoring), and contextual (self-management) processes in constructing and confirming meaningful and worthwhile learning outcomes.

Figure 2: Garrison’s Model of Self Directed Learning

Motivation: The motivational dimension is imperative in the learning process, calling for the learner to expect an outcome of their learning which will be beneficial to them. Not only do learners have to invest in their learning activities, but they have to persevere throughout the experience until the learning has been acquired

Self monitoring: Self-monitoring requires responsibility of the learner to acquire comprehension and understanding, ensuring that learning activities have value and learning objectives are being accomplished.

Self Management: Self-management concentrates on the external social and behavioural effects of learning transactions, goal setting, different types of learning approaches and establishing learning results.

Self Directed Learning provides for opportunities of meaning during learning interactions and without it, one may question the value in acquiring knowledge. Nonetheless, Self Directed Learning does not take away the expectation of the teacher, but requires the teacher to provide the educational desires that facilitate a Self Directed Learner

3.3.3 Self Directed Learning Skills

1. **Skill of identification of need for learning:** This skill involves the ability of the pupil to identify the component to be learnt, classify it into smaller learning units and establish the need for its learning
2. **Skill of formulation of goals for learning :** This skill involves the ability of the pupil to

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describe the learning in observable behavioural terms and specify the goal of learning

3. **Skill of identification of activities leading to the learning:** This skill involves the ability of the student to identify and list the activities which lead him/her to learning.
4. **Skill of identification of resources for learning:** This skill involves the ability of the student to identify the resources which lead him/her to learning.
5. **Skill of planning the learning process:** This skill involves the ability of the student to plan out strategies for learning.
6. **Skill of managing the learning process:** This skill involves the ability of the student to manage the activities that he/she has identified which can lead him/her to learning.
7. **Skill of evaluation:** This skill involves the ability of the student to formulate appropriate criteria to evaluate the authenticity of the learning that has taken place and evaluate her/his own learning.

3.3.4 Self-Directed Learning: A Four-Step Process

Self-directed learning can be challenging even for the brightest and most motivated students.

Being ready to learn: Signs of readiness for self-directed learning include being autonomous, organised, self-disciplined, able to communicate effectively, able to accept constructive feedback and engage in self-evaluation and self-reflection.

Setting learning goals: Communication of learning goals between a student and the facilitator includes structure and sequence of learning activities, timeline for completion of activities, details about resource materials for each goal, details about grading procedures, and a plan for regular meetings with the facilitator.

Engaging in the learning process: Students need to understand themselves’ as learners in order to understand their needs as self-directed learning students. Students also need to understand their approach to studying:

- **Deep approach** involves transforming wherein the learner understands ideas for self. This is the most ideal for self-directed learning.
- **Surface approach** involves reproducing wherein the learner is able to cope up with the requirements.
- **Strategic approach** involves organizing the learning material

Evaluating learning: Students must be able to engage in self-reflection and self-evaluation of

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learning goals and progress, regularly consult with the facilitator, engage in self-validation of achievements, motivation to seek feedback on progress and ideas

4.0 Opportunities to encourage and promote Self-Directed Learning among learners

- Challenge ideas without better clarity
- Observe clearly, interpret and draw conclusions
- Question certain thoughts which require further clarification
- Revise a question based on observation & data
- Modify something and improve a design
- Identify a cause and effect and separate causes from symptoms
- Compare and contrast two or more things
- Identify the primary and secondary causes of a problem
- Adapt something for a change or innovation
- Make a prediction and observe what occurs
- Extract a lesson from nature and narrate a sequence
- Identify and explain a pattern
- Critically evaluate a socially-accepted idea and take and defend a position
- Record notes during and after observation of something

Implications of Self Directed Learning to Education

- Learners should carry out a self assessment of their readiness to learn. This helps them to recognize their self awareness and their attitude towards the learning process.
- Learners should be able to define learning goals and build up on their learning process. Here the learner is expected to have a self-assessment and monitoring of the course of learning.
- Learners need to be voluntary and take initiative for all stages of learning process. Self motivation is an important factor to achieve this.
- The learner should always discuss with the facilitator as and when required to verify the precision and accuracy of the learning that is taking place. Based on this, evaluation and self reflection of the entire process of learning should be carried out.
- The teachers ought to build a co-operative learning environment, help to motivate and direct the students’ learning experience to be more satisfactory and meaningful, realising their learning styles with goal-setting strategy. This will boost the morale of the learners both

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cognitively and emotionally.

- Students’ initiatives for learning should be facilitated by the teacher or the instructor and guide accordingly and appropriately during the learning process towards proper planning, organizing and evaluating skills.
- Assist learners set their own goals by channelling the learning needs into clear, realistic and achievable learning objectives.
- The Learning activities provided to learner should build characteristics of an individual such as creativity, critical reflection, motivation, resilience, self-concept and self-evaluation from an early age so that the learner will be equipped with skills of “Self-directed Learning”.
- There needs to be provision for group decision making in the classroom in order to promote self-consciousness and responsibility among the learners.
- Train students for Self-evaluation by asking questions such as
 - How do I know I’ve well-read?
 - Am I flexible in adapting and applying knowledge?
 - Do I have self-confidence in elucidation of material?
 - When do I know I’ve learned adequate?
 - Is it time for self reflection?

Issues and Recommendations for further research

- Additional research is necessary to measure conceptual ideas based on the PRO model and other emerging ideas to give rise to a new theory on self-directed learning.
- Strategies need to be identified wherein educators can facilitate self-directed learning and promote critical thinking skills. Smith and Associates (1990) described how learners can be helped to learn, ask critical questions and reflect on what they are learning.
- It is important that better ways of incorporating computer technology and electronic communication into self-directed learning is determined as more distance education programs are created.
- Future research is needed on such issues as expanding the repertoire of design and methodology for studying self-directed learning, how competencies necessary for effective self-directed learning are developed and how the quality of self-directed learning resources can be measured.

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- Ways of measuring and maintaining quality in self-directed learning need to be determined.
- The most appropriate roles for educators and educational organizations in relation to self-directed learning need to be found.
- Finally, ways for learners and others to evaluate the value and effectiveness of self-directed learning need to be developed.
- Measures to assess learners self directed learning orientations.
- Developing various strategies on strengthening self directed learning abilities

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